

Supplementary Materials

Supplementary Materials for: Forecasting Australian Mental Health Service Demand with Distribution-Free Prediction Intervals

Hayden Farquhar MBBS MPHTM
Independent researcher, Finley, NSW, Australia
ORCID: 0009-0002-6226-440X

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table S1. Base forecast model holdout MAE (mean absolute error, services per 1,000 population). Hold-out period: Q3 2023–Q2 2024. Best-performing model per series shown in bold.

Domain	Series	ARIMA (order)	ETS	Prophet	Ensemble
MBS	All providers	6.91 (3,1,2)	9.22	11.70	9.27
MBS	Clinical psychologists	2.07 (2,1,2)	1.79	5.80	3.17
MBS	GPs	1.71 (1,1,0)	0.78	1.13	1.15
MBS	Other allied health	0.39 (3,1,2)	0.25	1.32	0.60
MBS	Other psychologists	3.04 (3,2,2)	2.47	6.37	3.76
MBS	Psychiatrists	0.78 (1,1,1)	0.56	0.45	0.51
PBS	All medications	2.55 (2,2,1)	5.11	8.71	3.51
PBS	Antidepressants	0.88 (2,2,1)	3.21	14.07	5.35
PBS	Antipsychotics	0.70 (0,1,1)	0.98	1.15	0.94
PBS	Anxiolytics	1.13 (0,2,2)	0.90	0.75	0.89
PBS	Hypnotics/sedatives	0.49 (3,2,1)	0.51	0.53	0.51
PBS	Psychostimulants (ADHD)	0.48 (0,2,2)	0.84	1.95	0.93

Supplementary Table S2. Full ITS results for all 23 intervention \times series combinations are available in the code repository (doi:10.5281/zenodo.19646929).

Supplementary Table S3. Conformal prediction interval empirical coverage (%) and mean width (services per 1,000) on the hold-out period, by series and method. Nominal coverage: 90% and 95%.

Series	90% Nominal				95% Nominal			
	ACI		EnbPI		ACI		EnbPI	
	Cov.	Width	Cov.	Width	Cov.	Width	Cov.	Width
MBS – All providers	75	16.1	75	14.5	100	19.2	75	33.9
MBS – Clinical psych.	75	5.4	75	5.3	75	6.1	75	6.3
MBS – GPs	75	6.3	75	6.6	100	7.5	75	10.9
MBS – Other allied health	100	2.1	100	2.1	100	2.2	100	2.3
MBS – Other psych.	75	4.8	50	6.7	100	8.8	100	7.5
MBS – Psychiatrists	100	3.6	100	3.6	100	4.5	100	4.4
PBS – All medications	100	34.1	100	36.0	100	52.2	100	198.3
PBS – Antidepressants	100	31.2	100	33.5	100	35.5	100	71.4
PBS – Antipsychotics	100	2.4	100	2.3	100	3.6	100	13.6
PBS – Anxiolytics	100	2.4	100	2.7	100	4.4	100	8.9
PBS – Hypnotics/sedatives	100	2.3	75	1.9	100	2.8	100	3.1
PBS – Psychostimulants	75	3.1	75	3.2	75	3.7	75	4.7

Supplementary Table S4. PELT changepoints across penalty sensitivity analysis (multipliers 0.5, 1.0, 2.0) are available in the code repository.

Supplementary Table S5. PHN-level mental health prescribing classification for all 31 PHNs is available in the code repository.

Supplementary Figures – Conformal Prediction Forecasts

Figure 1: Supplementary Figure S1. Conformal prediction forecast for MBS – All providers with ACI 90% and 95% prediction intervals through mid-2027.

Figure 2: Supplementary Figure S2. Conformal prediction forecast for MBS – Clinical psychologists with ACI 90% and 95% prediction intervals through mid-2027.

Figure 3: Supplementary Figure S3. Conformal prediction forecast for MBS – GPs with ACI 90% and 95% prediction intervals through mid-2027.

Figure 4: Supplementary Figure S4. Conformal prediction forecast for MBS – Other allied health with ACI 90% and 95% prediction intervals through mid-2027.

Figure 5: Supplementary Figure S5. Conformal prediction forecast for MBS – Other psychologists with ACI 90% and 95% prediction intervals through mid-2027.

Figure 6: Supplementary Figure S6. Conformal prediction forecast for MBS – Psychiatrists with ACI 90% and 95% prediction intervals through mid-2027.

Figure 7: Supplementary Figure S7. Conformal prediction forecast for PBS – All medications with ACI 90% and 95% prediction intervals through mid-2027.

Figure 8: Supplementary Figure S8. Conformal prediction forecast for PBS – Antidepressants with ACI 90% and 95% prediction intervals through mid-2027.

Figure 9: Supplementary Figure S9. Conformal prediction forecast for PBS – Antipsychotics with ACI 90% and 95% prediction intervals through mid-2027.

Figure 10: Supplementary Figure S10. Conformal prediction forecast for PBS – Anxiolytics with ACI 90% and 95% prediction intervals through mid-2027.

Figure 11: Supplementary Figure S11. Conformal prediction forecast for PBS – Hypnotics/Sedatives with ACI 90% and 95% prediction intervals through mid-2027.

Figure 12: Supplementary Figure S12. Conformal prediction forecast for PBS – Psychostimulants (ADHD) with ACI 90% and 95% prediction intervals through mid-2027.

Supplementary Figures – STL Decomposition

Figure 13: Supplementary Figure S13. STL decomposition (trend, seasonal, residual) for MBS – All providers, quarterly 2014–2024.

Figure 14: Supplementary Figure S14. STL decomposition (trend, seasonal, residual) for MBS – Clinical psychologists, quarterly 2014–2024.

Figure 15: Supplementary Figure S15. STL decomposition (trend, seasonal, residual) for MBS – GPs, quarterly 2014–2024.

Figure 16: Supplementary Figure S16. STL decomposition (trend, seasonal, residual) for MBS – Other allied health, quarterly 2014–2024.

Figure 17: Supplementary Figure S17. STL decomposition (trend, seasonal, residual) for MBS – Other psychologists, quarterly 2014–2024.

Figure 18: Supplementary Figure S18. STL decomposition (trend, seasonal, residual) for MBS – Psychiatrists, quarterly 2014–2024.

Figure 19: Supplementary Figure S19. STL decomposition (trend, seasonal, residual) for PBS – All medications, quarterly 2014–2024.

Figure 20: Supplementary Figure S20. STL decomposition (trend, seasonal, residual) for PBS – Antidepressants, quarterly 2014–2024.

Figure 21: Supplementary Figure S21. STL decomposition (trend, seasonal, residual) for PBS – Antipsychotics, quarterly 2014–2024.

Figure 22: Supplementary Figure S22. STL decomposition (trend, seasonal, residual) for PBS – Anxiolytics, quarterly 2014–2024.

Figure 23: Supplementary Figure S23. STL decomposition (trend, seasonal, residual) for PBS – Hypnotics/Sedatives, quarterly 2014–2024.

Figure 24: Supplementary Figure S24. STL decomposition (trend, seasonal, residual) for PBS – Psychostimulants (ADHD), quarterly 2014–2024.

Supplementary Figures – Changepoint Detection

Figure 25: Supplementary Figure S25. PELT changepoint detection with BOCPD probability overlay for MBS – All providers.

Figure 26: Supplementary Figure S26. PELT changepoint detection with BOCPD probability overlay for MBS – Clinical psychologists.

Figure 27: Supplementary Figure S27. PELT changepoint detection with BOCPD probability overlay for MBS – GPs.

Figure 28: Supplementary Figure S28. PELT changepoint detection with BOCPD probability overlay for MBS – Other allied health.

Figure 29: Supplementary Figure S29. PELT changepoint detection with BOCPD probability overlay for MBS – Other psychologists.

Figure 30: Supplementary Figure S30. PELT changepoint detection with BOCPD probability overlay for MBS – Psychiatrists.

Figure 31: Supplementary Figure S31. PELT changepoint detection with BOCPD probability overlay for PBS – All medications.

Figure 32: Supplementary Figure S32. PELT changepoint detection with BOCPD probability overlay for PBS – Antidepressants.

Figure 33: Supplementary Figure S33. PELT changepoint detection with BOCPD probability overlay for PBS – Antipsychotics.

Figure 34: Supplementary Figure S34. PELT changepoint detection with BOCPD probability overlay for PBS – Anxiolytics.

Figure 35: Supplementary Figure S35. PELT changepoint detection with BOCPD probability overlay for PBS – Hypnotics/Sedatives.

Figure 36: Supplementary Figure S36. PELT changepoint detection with BOCPD probability overlay for PBS – Psychostimulants (ADHD).

Supplementary Figures – ITS: COVID-19 Onset

Figure 37: Supplementary Figure S37. ITS analysis of COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020) for MBS – All providers.

Figure 38: Supplementary Figure S38. ITS analysis of COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020) for MBS – Clinical psychologists.

Figure 39: Supplementary Figure S39. ITS analysis of COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020) for MBS – GPs.

Figure 40: Supplementary Figure S40. ITS analysis of COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020) for MBS – Other allied health.

Figure 41: Supplementary Figure S41. ITS analysis of COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020) for MBS – Other psychologists.

Figure 42: Supplementary Figure S42. ITS analysis of COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020) for MBS – Psychiatrists.

Figure 43: Supplementary Figure S43. ITS analysis of COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020) for PBS – All medications.

Figure 44: Supplementary Figure S44. ITS analysis of COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020) for PBS – Antidepressants.

Figure 45: Supplementary Figure S45. ITS analysis of COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020) for PBS – Antipsychotics.

Figure 46: Supplementary Figure S46. ITS analysis of COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020) for PBS – Anxiolytics.

Figure 47: Supplementary Figure S47. ITS analysis of COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020) for PBS – Hypnotics/Sedatives.

Figure 48: Supplementary Figure S48. ITS analysis of COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020) for PBS – Psychostimulants (ADHD).

Supplementary Figures – ITS: Better Access Session Reduction

Figure 49: Supplementary Figure S49. ITS analysis of Better Access session reduction (January 2023) for MBS – All providers.

Figure 50: Supplementary Figure S50. ITS analysis of Better Access session reduction (January 2023) for MBS – Clinical psychologists.

Figure 51: Supplementary Figure S51. ITS analysis of Better Access session reduction (January 2023) for MBS – GPs.

Figure 52: Supplementary Figure S52. ITS analysis of Better Access session reduction (January 2023) for MBS – Other psychologists.

Supplementary Figures – ITS: 60-Day Dispensing Reform

Figure 53: Supplementary Figure S53. ITS analysis of 60-day dispensing reform (October 2023) for PBS – All medications.

Figure 54: Supplementary Figure S54. ITS analysis of 60-day dispensing reform (October 2023) for PBS – Antidepressants.

Figure 55: Supplementary Figure S55. ITS analysis of 60-day dispensing reform (October 2023) for PBS – Antipsychotics.

Figure 56: Supplementary Figure S56. ITS analysis of 60-day dispensing reform (October 2023) for PBS – Anxiolytics.

Figure 57: Supplementary Figure S57. ITS analysis of 60-day dispensing reform (October 2023) for PBS – Hypnotics/Sedatives.

Supplementary Figures – Base Forecast Comparisons

Figure 58: Supplementary Figure S58. Base forecast comparison (ARIMA, ETS, Prophet, Ensemble) for MBS – All providers.

Figure 59: Supplementary Figure S59. Base forecast comparison (ARIMA, ETS, Prophet, Ensemble) for MBS – Clinical psychologists.

Figure 60: Supplementary Figure S60. Base forecast comparison (ARIMA, ETS, Prophet, Ensemble) for MBS – GPs.

Figure 61: Supplementary Figure S61. Base forecast comparison (ARIMA, ETS, Prophet, Ensemble) for MBS – Other allied health.

Figure 62: Supplementary Figure S62. Base forecast comparison (ARIMA, ETS, Prophet, Ensemble) for MBS – Other psychologists.

Figure 63: Supplementary Figure S63. Base forecast comparison (ARIMA, ETS, Prophet, Ensemble) for MBS – Psychiatrists.

Figure 64: Supplementary Figure S64. Base forecast comparison (ARIMA, ETS, Prophet, Ensemble) for PBS – All medications.

Figure 65: Supplementary Figure S65. Base forecast comparison (ARIMA, ETS, Prophet, Ensemble) for PBS – Antidepressants.

Figure 66: Supplementary Figure S66. Base forecast comparison (ARIMA, ETS, Prophet, Ensemble) for PBS – Antipsychotics.

Figure 67: Supplementary Figure S67. Base forecast comparison (ARIMA, ETS, Prophet, Ensemble) for PBS – Anxiolytics.

Figure 68: Supplementary Figure S68. Base forecast comparison (ARIMA, ETS, Prophet, Ensemble) for PBS – Hypnotics/Sedatives.

Figure 69: Supplementary Figure S69. Base forecast comparison (ARIMA, ETS, Prophet, Ensemble) for PBS – Psychostimulants (ADHD).

Supplementary Figures – Additional

Figure 70: Supplementary Figure S70. Overview of all 12 national quarterly time series (raw rates per 1,000).

Figure 71: Supplementary Figure S71. Geographic variation in mental health prescribing over time: Gini coefficient, coefficient of variation, and rate range.

Figure 72: Supplementary Figure S72. PHN x year heatmap of mental health prescribing rates (z-scored).